

EARTH SCIENCES

ASSESSMENT OF SEDIMENTATION BASED ON THE RESULTS OF GEOPHYSICAL LOG ANALYSIS

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Abstract

Sediment accumulation is a complex process and the study of the origin, formation conditions, composition, and characteristics of the collected sediments is one of the main issues. Conditions of sediment accumulation means as an environment that differs from the environment as a limited geographical area due to its physical, chemical and biological characteristics, and continental, marine, transitional areas can occur.

Sediment accumulation conditions are unique climate change, erosion conditions on the earth's surface due to the action of running water, fauna and flora, underwater conditions - temperature, basin depth, salinity, etc. characterized by characteristics and dynamically related to each other. That is, according to the change of any of them, another parameter changes.

The main part of the oil and gas fields discovered in Azerbaijan is related to terrigenous sediments, a more detailed analysis of these sediments is of great theoretical and practical importance. [1]

Keywords: lithofacies analysis, geophysical logging, sedimentary rocks, quantitative model of the logging, sediment accumulation, facies, flow, bar, coastal plain.

The facies analysis method conducted in deep drilling wells is one of the most common and accurate types of research. This method is based on gamma ray (GR) and self-potential (SP) log data and the study of sediment distribution characteristics. It allows to research in more detail the formation conditions of terrigenous sediments in order to detect oil and gas deposits. [2]

Taking into account the diversity of facies conditions and at the same time the limitation of the generalized forms of SP (GR) curves, it is possible to carry out the interpretation in a certain sequence. After determining the facies group of the studied sediments, the condition of sediment flows according to the forms of the SP (GR) of the considered group is determined based on the logging curves.

A distribution model of facies conditions is selected on the basis of well logging analysis. This model, the facies in the accumulation conditions are compared with the core material. As a result, this comparison makes it possible not only to research the relationship of sediment accumulation conditions detected during drilling with the area, but also to explain the formation conditions of facies based on well data. [3]

But, the determined porosity, permeability, clay content, drilling mud and granulometric content, degree of mineralization of formation water, etc., influence the interpretation of the curves. For this reason, it is possible to obtain more accurate results when using the lithological changes of the layers along with the logging curves. Diagrams of the complex of well geophysical research methods based on the quantitative

model of the logging facies and at the same time the relative clay coefficient and the effective porosity coefficient change depending on the depth. It is possible to study the lithological composition of rocks, as well as the origin of sediments and conditions of sediment accumulation in more detail. Depending on the depth, the change of the relative clay coefficient and the effective porosity coefficient allows to divide the genetic origin of the sediments into 3 places according to the SP (GR) logging curves: flow, bar and coastal. [4]

According to the quantitative model of the logging facies, the well logging diagrams and the curves of the variation of the relative clay coefficient and the effective porosity coefficient depending on the depth were analyzed together.

In the Hazi Aslanov field (Fig. 1), the lithofacies analysis of the productive layers was carried out and the genetic origin of the sedimentary rocks was determined. Based on the complex logging diagrams, the effective porosity coefficient and volume clay coefficient of the rocks were calculated in the cross-sections we research (table 1).

Determination of effective porosity in the researched rock samples was calculated by the formula:

$$K_{por} = K_p - K_p^{cl} K_{cl} \quad (1)$$

Determination of relative clay:

$$K_{clay} = (1 - C_{sand})(1 - K_{por}) \quad (2)$$

The facies analysis of the sediments was carried out in the research wells on the layers of the productive layer, and according to the results, the thickness of the coastal, flow and bar plain facies were determined.

Figure 1. Conditional X-1 well of H. Aslanov field.

Table 1.

Depth interval, m	Layer group.	H.Aslanov (X-1)	
		K _{clay}	K _{por}
1280.4-1289.3	QD (1047.0-1378.0)	0.385	0.189
1297.5-1300.9		0.387	0.208
1335.6-1337.1		0.355	0.227
1372.2-1375.9		0.314	0.224
1379-1383.9	QA (1378.0-1675.0)	0.389	0.219
1436.3-1439.4		0.378	0.223
1463.9-1468.3		0.325	0.162
1489.0-1491.0		0.120	0.224
1502.2-1515.0		0.137	0.157
1545.6-1554.3		0.144	0.158

Values of effective porosity and clay coefficient were determined for the researched well sections.

In the Hazi Aslanov structure, according to the quantitative interpretation of conventional well cross-

section No. 1, two strata are separated in the researched cross section interval. These formations are QD and QA. (Fig.2)

Figure. 2. Depth dependence histograms of parameters of effective porosity (K_{por}) and relative clay (K_{clay}) in the researched profile.

After the depth of 1450 m, it was determined that the effective porosity increased and the clay content decreased, and due to their genetic origin, these layers were attributed to flow-originated facies. The layers researched here are located in the QA-layer group. According to the characteristics of saturation, these layers belong to collectors. And in some intervals (for example, at 1500-1560 m) oil reservoirs were found.

It has been known that facies of flow originated also persist in the lower intervals. In these intervals, there is an increase in effective porosity, as well as a decrease in clay content. Also, the layers here belong to reservoirs due to their saturation characteristics, and lithologically, we can say that they consist of sandstones, siltstones and clays. [5]

Models have been built in the research works, and 3D models showing the variation of porosity and clay. (Fig.3, Fig.4)

Based on the created models, it was determined that the value of the effective porosity in the well in the Hazi Aslanov field along the QD formation is the maximum in the central part, and this value decreases to the minimum towards the western part.

The variation of the porosity coefficient across the QA formation decreases from west to east. The maximum price is marked around the conditional 1 well. Based on the facies analysis, facies of flow and bar originated were determined in the QA formation.

It is also observed that towards the east, around the conditional 1 well, the sand content decreases, while the clay content increases, on the contrary. In the QA formation, the maximum value of sandiness is distinguished in the west, while the value of the clay coefficient increases towards the east.

Figure 3. The model characterizing the porosity of the Hazi Aslanov structure.

Figure 4. The model characterizing the clayness of the Hazi Aslanov structure.

On the basis of the well data, the change of the flow, bar and coastal plain facies of the QD, QA layers of the productive series along the research profile was evaluated, and the results are given in table 2.

Thickness of facies of flow, bar and coastal plain origin in QD, QA formations of productive layer.

Table 2.

Deposit	Layer group	The thickness of the flow originated facies, m	The thickness of the bar originated facies, m	The thickness of the coastal plain originated facies, m
H.Aslanov	QD	0	140	56
	QA	127	32	0

Conclusions

1. Effective porosity and relative clay values were calculated for each well section taken on the basis of complex well data, and then histograms of these parameters were constructed by depth.

2. By using the quantitative model of the logging facies, lithofacies analysis of the sedimentary rocks was carried out on the wells located on the research profile of the deposits, and facies of stream, bar and coastal plain origin were determined.

3. It was determined that in the QD formation in the Hazi Aslanov field, the thickness of the bar origin facies prevails (140 m), while in the QA formation, it decreases to 32 m. Facies of flow origin prevailed in the QA formation (127 m).

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